

THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS AT SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *In the given article the use of advanced pedagogical technologies and the use of modern interactive methods when conducting mathematics lessons in primary school, to increase the effectiveness of learning and increase students' interest in the lesson are discussed.*

Keywords: *primary education, methodology, pedagogical technologies, didactic games, interactive methods.*

The 21st century is the century of innovation in the field of science. At present time many changes in science are observed in hundreds of regions. In addition, developments in the field of mathematics reach the highest level. The research carried out within this discipline makes a great contribution to the development of time. At the same time, it is important to pay attention to the teaching of mathematics in our country.

It is known to everyone that the science of teaching mathematics is a specific branch of the science of pedagogy that deals with the study of the rules of teaching mathematics. In the process of studying the laws of teaching mathematics, the methodology of teaching mathematics is in an integral connection with the sciences of pedagogy, logic, psychology, mathematics, linguistics and philosophy. In other words, the problems of teaching mathematics at school are solved in inextricable connection with the sciences of logic, psychology, pedagogy, mathematics and philosophy. The methodological basis for teaching mathematics is the theory of knowledge. The science of mathematical methodology studies the purpose, content, form, method and methods of applying mathematical education in the educational process. Mathematics is physics. It is closely related to the sciences of drawing, chemistry and astronomy.

It is not a secret that in a number of developed countries, the use of didactic games and interactive methods is successfully used to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. Lessons are taught using such interactive methods and didactic games are very interesting and, together with the full involvement of students in the lesson, open an excellent way for their independent thinking and free expression of their speech.

There are many types of didactic games and interactive methods that are widely used to implement almost all tasks of the educational process. Interactive methods mean methods that activate students and encourage them to think independently, with the student at the center of the educational process. Using such methods, the teacher invites the student to actively participate. The student is involved throughout the entire process.

Interactive methods are divided into theoretical, practical, role-playing, physical, labor and several types. Thus, students improve their knowledge in the field of measurement, calculation, analysis, testing, comparison, drawing conclusions and making independent decisions. Benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- Training with the highest educational effect;
- High student motivation;

- Taking into account previously acquired knowledge;
- Bringing the educational process in line with the target needs of the student;
- Supporting student initiative and responsibility;
- On-the-job training;
- Creating conditions for two-way feedback.

Another aspect of mathematics lessons is the abstract nature of the teaching material. Therefore, it also depends on visual aids, careful selection of active teaching methods, student activity, and skill level of students in the class. The math class also addresses various regional educational challenges. It instills in students' observation, intelligence, a critical look at the environment, initiative in work, responsibility, accuracy in calculations, measurements and accounting, hard work and overcoming difficulties.

The forms of work and lesson listed here complement each other. The main question concerns the lesson. All work in the lesson is controlled directly by the teacher. In additional classes, work is done by the teacher himself or by students under the guidance of a teacher.

The situation that needs to be justified today is to provide pedagogical support to the student and to find convenient forms and opportunities for pedagogical support in the learning process.

One of the factors in increasing the activity of students and developing their interest in mathematics in the process of learning mathematics is independent work with students.

During Mathematics lessons, independent work is carried out to prepare for studying new material, getting acquainted with new concepts, consolidating knowledge, mastering skills, and also monitoring knowledge. Organizational forms of teaching mathematics in primary school consist of lessons, independent homework, individual work of students in groups and teams, excursions, and extracurricular activities.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that improving the literacy of methods of teaching mathematics in primary classes is one of the requirements of the time. Due to the use of mass information technologies and interactive methods at mathematics lessons, the relationship between teacher and student becomes more consistent, collective harmony and an effective educational process are established. For such a complex process, the formation of theoretical knowledge and practical skills of teachers is of great importance.

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